

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF USING INTEGRATION IN LITERATURE TEACHING

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ANNOTATION

Literature is a complex and multidisciplinary field of study that introduces students to life. It improves their ability to understand the complexity of the environment and human character, the feeling of loyalty to the motherland . Develops imagination and thinking about the world .

Key words: integration, differentiation, curriculum , integration of activities

Integration is the opposite of differentiation . It is advisable to implement it in the following directions : a) integrated learning of the content within the educational subjects and disciplines; b) integration of the activities of persons teaching different educational subjects; c) forms of organization of educational work or integration of the educational day.

Integration creates an opportunity and conditions for the development of thinking. Integration is an important means of individual work with the student and his activation. As a result of the organization of interdisciplinary communication in lessons, the number of educational subjects will be reduced, the effect will be more thorough, it will be easier to attract students to independent work.

to teach imagination , to organize intergroup competitions, and question-and-answer sessions.

using such modern types of lessons is to stabilize the activity of students in the educational process, to achieve a high level of mastering the educational material. Such technology teaches students to imagine the world in a different way. To connect practice with life , not to memorize theoretical rules verbatim, that is, from scholasticism forces to escape. It makes it possible to understand the harmony of the individual and society , to achieve diversity of thoughts, to think non-standard, and also to understand the ways of self-development.

Researcher BSAbdullayeva divides interdisciplinary communication into the following types: 1) meaningful; 2) operational; 3) methodological; 4) organizational. Integration is consistent with the following ideas of Fariduddin Attar: in this world, there is no small thing alone, everything is interconnected and complements each other. The lesson should not be only educational , but should be aimed at educating students in humanitarian aspects. Literature is a complex and multifaceted academic subject. It introduces students to life, develops in them the ability to understand the complexity of the environment and human character, and the feeling of loyalty to the Motherland and people.

The content of studying the language features of the artistic text should form a whole mechanism, using the theoretical concepts and information learned in literature classes on the basis of integration. This mechanism should be ensured by the consistency of the types of

work that serve to teach the knowledge, which is selected in accordance with the educational goals, to transform them into skills and competences.

It is permissible to use modular lesson technologies to teach literature lessons in connection with the idea of national independence, etiquette, as well as painting and drawing. Because such classes teach students to strive for creativity and independent thinking.

The teacher's creativity is that they first of all organize the aspects that are known to the subject, but the student does not know, and encourage their students to do the same. As long as this is the case, it is understood that the implementation of integration through the organization of module lessons is an effective way to develop thinking in literature students .

Integration does not seem to be necessary in imparting knowledge, but it is a way to broaden one's understanding of the world, through which the students' worldview is broadened: a deep understanding of the laws of language, art, history, music, manners, and literature . understands, knows the relationship. It is part of the modern methods of teaching students to be creative, directing them to research, generating imagination and fantasy. Poems from literature can be improved through language lessons . We try to share our opinions on how to conduct literature classes on the basis of integration . In order to organize integrated classes, the teacher determines the ways to increase the activity of students, the methods of passing the topic, and the tools that should be used during the training process. In the implementation of these works, consistent requirements for the subject should be made . For this purpose, the teacher prepares an extended plan of the lesson and works on the basis of this plan. Students are challenged individually through independent thinking, resulting in the development of critical thinking skills.

Methodologists B.Ziyomhammadov and Sh.Abdullayeva emphasize that the technology of the educational process should be developed for one lesson, one subject or a part of the educational subject, the entire educational subject, and show that it has 5 main principles .

The first is to formulate the main goal expected from a specific lesson, topic, section, educational subject; the second is to divide the lesson or educational subject into modules and determine the goals expected from each module and the system of issues to be solved within the modules; the third is to create test questions within the module; the fourth is to determine the methods of achieving the goals, the fifth is to pay special attention to the necessary connections between the parts of the lesson and interdisciplinary relations, based on the principle of unity ¹.

In order to increase the effectiveness of education, it is necessary to create integrated programs and textbooks. Educator U. Musayev offers different levels of integration as follows ².

Integration based on sequential presentation of topics; in this case , the principle of concentricity is followed in the presentation of educational materials, that is, the previous educational material complements the next one.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above opinions regarding the organization of integrated classes:

¹Ziyamhammadov B., Abdullaeva Sh. Advanced pedagogical technology.- T.: Abu Ali ibn Sina, 2001.-B. 24-25.

²Musaev U. Levels of integration // Public education. - 2002 - No. 6.- B. 5-6.

1. Integration based on the creation of mutually compatible points in educational programs, that is, ensures inter-subject harmony . It is appropriate to teach topics and texts related to history and literature, the idea of national independence , and botany in mother tongue classes.

2. In modular integration, knowledge and concepts related to related academic subjects are given in a systematic way.

the teaching materials provided in one course are carried out in harmony with the teaching materials of a similar subject in another course.

, the effectiveness of education increases and unnecessary expenditure of effort and stress is prevented. The goal of today's education is to educate a creative person who can reveal all his potential. It is an innovative concept that accomplishes this goal— requiring changes within the system.

This concept means "innovation" and means the transition from totalitarian to democratic education system, taking into account the interests and abilities of the individual, humanizing education, adapting the education system to the economic conditions of the society. it is necessary to take into account such things as creating conditions for the formation of an educational system that ensures deep assimilation of knowledge ³.

educational methods serve to show students' abilities, sharpen their minds, and develop their thinking . For this purpose, the use of poetic art, interpretation and explanation of the topics being studied is an acceptable way . These methods serve to motivate the student , to increase his interest in learning and to show his ability.

To ensure that the educational process corresponds to the educational goal, it is necessary to achieve the following:

Implementation of new educational models based on the educational content in the educational process based on the demand in the society and the purpose of education . One of the main goals should be to ensure the student's activity in the learning process . In addition, it is to expand the directions of the educational content that are proportional to the goal of education and ensure the orientation of the individual, as well as to ensure interdisciplinarity ⁴. In reality, the unity of purpose and content should be reflected in education , that is: a) teaching to feel existence; b) developing the skills of teachers in using modern methods of teaching in accordance with educational goals and content; c) getting used to learning due to need; g) it is necessary to properly organize students' independent education. In the process of completing assignments, students can put events and phenomena, their explanations and proofs into a single system, draw conclusions, generalize, imagine and fantasize . For this, it is appropriate to give assignments aimed at developing the personality of the student . Such assignments provide an opportunity to properly organize the educational process focused on the student's personality . Theoretical analysis and practical observations are carried out.

It is known that any science can arise under the influence of the sciences close to it and develop together with them . After the science of philosophy, which uniquely gathered the knowledge gathered in literature classes, especially during the renaissance period, in the advanced conditions of human knowledge, independent branches of science began to

³ Yoldasheva D. Possibilities of determining the content of education according to the purpose of education //Continuing education. Tashkent, 2007 No. 2. Page 7.

⁴Yoldasheva D. Possibilities of determining the content of education according to the purpose of education //Continuing education. Tashkent, 2007. No. 2. 25 p

separate, as a result, the process of stratification of sciences began, which, in turn, became the school itself . began to break the natural dialectical relations between subjects and phenomena of the world. This leads to scholastic knowledge, such as a narrowing of the perception of the interconnectedness and interrelationships of things and phenomena in nature .

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